

Effect of Vermicompost Applications on Quality, Yield and Some Macro and Micro Elements Content of Bread Wheat

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the effect of different rates of vermicompost applied to the soil on yield and certain yield characteristics of bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). The research was conducted under Mardin conditions during the 2019-2020 production season. The study used varying rates of vermicompost and two wheat varieties, Dinç and Tekin, as plant materials. The experiment was set up in a factorial design with three replications. The rates of vermicompost applied were 0, 100, 200, and 300 kg da⁻¹. The study evaluated protein content per grain, starch content per grain, macro and micro element concentrations. After the production season, the plants were harvested, and necessary analyses and measurements were performed. The findings indicate that vermicompost applications affected the yield by 12.5% in the Dinç variety and 17.9% in the Tekin variety. In both wheat varieties, the highest protein content and the lowest starch content were observed with 300 kg da⁻¹ vermicompost applications, showing an increase in protein and a decrease in starch compared to the control (0 kg da⁻¹) groups. Overall, increasing vermicompost applications led to higher K and P levels in both wheat varieties compared to the control (0 kg da⁻¹). In the Dinç variety, Cu, Zn, and Fe concentrations increased with higher rates, while Mn concentration varied. In the Tekin variety, significant increases in Cu, Zn, Fe, and Mn concentrations were observed, with the highest levels of Cu, Zn, and Fe found at 300 kg da⁻¹.

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1. Introduction

Wheat has played a significant role in human nutrition since ancient times and continues to be a fundamental food source in many parts of the world. It provides more than half of the daily calorie needs for people and is the cereal crop with the highest protein content among field crops (Doğan and Kendal, 2013; Peng et al., 2011a,b; Anonymous, 2023). However, ensuring adequate food for the rapidly growing global population has become challenging, leading to the widespread use of agricultural chemicals and synthetic fertilizers for quick yield increases a phenomenon known as the "Green Revolution" (Shiferaw et al., 2013; Bisht and Chauhan, 2020; Baranski, 2022). Over time, the indiscriminate and excessive use of these chemicals has caused significant negative impacts on the natural environment and living organisms, leading to carcinogenic, mutagenic and teratogenic effects and the necessity to explore alternative agricultural methods (Baier-Anderson and Anderson, 2000; Beard, 2006). Excessive chemical use has accelerated soil degradation and desertification, negatively affecting soil flora and fauna. As a result, eco-friendly organic approaches that preserve ecological balance and rejuvenate nature have been developed to ensure the sustainability of agricultural production (Chen et al., 2001). Organic fertilizers, which are derived from plant, animal, and human residues, contribute to soil enrichment and improvement, supporting yield increases. Although these organic fertilizers may not be sufficient in mineral nutrients, they positively enhance the physical, chemical, and biological properties of the soil and are therefore important (Demir and Sönmez, 2019). Vermicomposting (VC) has been shown to have many benefits, including promoting plant growth, improving soil physical, chemical and biological properties and restoring natural fertility, making it effective in both organic and conventional agriculture (Singh and Chauhan, 2009). The primary aim of organic farming is to protect plant, environmental, human and animal health by reducing water, soil and air

pollution (Kızılaslan and Olgun, 2012). Among the steps taken to increase yield and maintain agricultural sustainability without negatively impacting the environment and living organisms, VC stands out as an effective and important organic fertilizer that enriches soil with organic matter and nutrients and serves as a good soil conditioner (Huang et al., 2013). Numerous scientific studies have reported improvements in crop yield and quality, as well as enhancements in soil biological, physical and chemical properties as a result of VC applications (Alam et al., 2007; Bai and Malakouti, 2007; Çıtak et al., 2011). This study investigated the effect of different vermicompost rates applied to the soil on the yield and certain yield characteristics of bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). The research was conducted under Mardin conditions during the 2019-2020 production season, evaluating the interactions between different vermicompost rates and wheat varieties.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Plant material

The plant varieties used in this study are Dinç and Tekin bread wheat, both of which are cultivated in our region. The Dinç and Tekin wheat varieties were registered in 2013 (Dinç: with an average yield of 300 kg da⁻¹ under optimal conditions, with a yield potential of up to 874 kg da⁻¹) and 2014 (Tekin: with an average yield of approximately 600 kg da⁻¹ under optimal conditions, with a yield potential of up to 800 kg da⁻¹) at the GAP International Agricultural Research and Training Center (GAP UTAEM).

2.2. Vermicompost

The VC used in the experiment has a pH of 7.20, which is slightly alkaline, and is below the damage threshold for pathogenic microorganisms, parasites, and heavy metals. This VC is particularly rich in organic matter and contains almost all essential nutrients required for plant growth, including P, Ca, Mn, Fe, Mg and humic/fulvic acids (Table 1).

Table 1. Composition of solid vermicompost

Properties	Solid Fertilizer
pH	7.20
Moisture%	40.0
Ash Content	42.0
Total Humic+Fulvic Acids	12.0
Organic Matter%	55.0
N%	1.60
P ₂ O ₅	2.20
Ca%	5.00
Mg%	1.20
Fe%	1.50
Mn (mg kg ⁻¹)	73.0
Pathogenic Microflora	-
Parasites	-
Heavy Metals (mg kg ⁻¹)	-

2.3. Soil properties of the experimental area

The experiment was conducted during the 2019-2020 growing season on a farmer's field in Tilki village, Mardin. The soil in the

experimental area has a pH of 7.43 and is classified as clay-loam with high lime content and no salinity issues. The soil analysis results are provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Some chemical and physical properties of the experimental soil

Properties	Experimental Soil	References
Texture	Clay-Loam	Bouyoucos, 1952
Salt (%)	0.23	Soil Survey Staff, 1951
CaCO ₃ (%)	38.5	Loeppert et al., 1996
Organic Matter (%)	1.45	Kacar, 1995
Total N (%)	0.89	Bremner, 1965
Available P (mg P ₂ O ₅ kg ⁻¹)	17.9	Olsen, 1954
Available K (mg K ₂ O kg ⁻¹)	82.3	Richards, 1954
Fe (mg kg ⁻¹)	23.9	
Cu (mg kg ⁻¹)	3.82	Lindsay and Norvell, 1978
Mn (mg kg ⁻¹)	71.7	(DTPA)
Zn (mg kg ⁻¹)	6.95	

2.4. Climate characteristics of the research area

In the Southeastern Anatolia region, a generally continental/Mediterranean climate prevails. In Mardin, the climate is significantly influenced by the high mountains in the north. The high-pressure areas that form in the region

cause colder conditions during winter. Monthly total precipitation, average temperature, humidity and wind data for the 2019-2020 growing season are provided in Table 3. According to the data, the highest amount of precipitation occurred in December, while the least amount was observed in June.

Table 3. Climate data for Mardin (2019/2020)*

Feature	2019 Oct.	2019 Nov.	2019 Dec.	2020 Jan.	2020 Feb.	2020 Mar.	2020 Apr.	2020 May.	2020 Jun.
Avg. Tem. (°C)	18.6	11.8	5.90	5.70	8.60	13.3	18.6	25.0	32.0
Humidity	11.8	6.2	1.50	71.0	71.0	63.0	53.0	43.0	27.0
Precipitation (mm)	37.0	66.0	99.0	66.0	53.0	61.0	70.0	44.0	2.00

(*): Mardin Meteorology Directorate

2.5. Experimental design

The experiment was set up using a factorial design with three replications. A total of 24 plots were established, with each plot measuring 2 m x 4 m = 8 m² and having a row spacing of 20 cm. The amount of seed sown was determined to be 450 seeds per square meter. The wheat varieties used in the experiment (Dinç and Tekin) were treated with VC rates of 0, 100, 200 and 300 kg da⁻¹. Sowing was carried out manually on November 15, 2019, with marked rows.

2.6. Measured parameters

Grain yield per unit area (kg da⁻¹) was calculated by converting the grain yield obtained from the 8 m² plots to per hectare. The protein and starch content (%) in the grains were measured using NIR spectroscopy. Macro and microelement (K, P, Fe, Mn, Cu, and Zn) concentrations in the grains were determined using an ICP-MS device.

2.7. Statistical analysis

Results from the experiment were analyzed according to the factorial design. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test whether the differences between group means were statistically significant. ANOVA evaluates the main effects of multiple factors (i.e., the effect of each factor individually) and interactions between factors (i.e., the combined effect of two or more factors). ANOVA analysis was performed using SPSS 22.0 statistical software, determining whether variances

between groups were significant at a confidence level of 95% (i.e., $p \leq 0.05$). Duncan's test was used to hierarchically rank the groups according to their means and identify significant differences. This process allows for a detailed examination of the results and reveals the effects of different treatments.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Correlation coefficients and significance levels

Correlation analysis revealed a negative relationship between starch and rate at $p \leq 0.05$, as well as between yield and protein at $p \leq 0.01$. Potassium (K) had a positive relationship with rate at $p \leq 0.01$. Negative relationships between K and starch were observed, while positive relationships with protein ($p \leq 0.01$) were found. Phosphorus (P) showed positive relationships with yield and protein at $p \leq 0.01$, and with K at $p \leq 0.05$. Copper (Cu) had positive relationships with yield, protein, K, and P at $p \leq 0.01$, and a negative relationship with starch at $p \leq 0.01$. Zinc (Zn) showed positive relationships with yield, protein, K, P, and Cu at $p \leq 0.01$, and with rate at $p \leq 0.05$, while having a negative relationship with starch at $p \leq 0.01$. Iron (Fe) was positively related to rate, protein, K, and Zn at $p \leq 0.01$, and to yield and P at $p \leq 0.05$, while being negatively related to starch at $p \leq 0.01$. Manganese (Mn) showed a positive relationship with yield at $p \leq 0.01$, but a negative relationship with rate at $p \leq 0.01$ and a positive relationship with protein at $p \leq 0.05$ (Table 4).

Table 4. Correlation coefficients and significance levels between parameters

Parameter	Rate	Yield	Protein	Starch	K	P	Cu	Zn	Fe	Mn
Rate	1									
Yield	-0.052	1								
Protein	0.208	.659**	1							
Starch	-.411*	-.575**	-.768**	1						
K	.827**	0.31	.582**	-.728**	1					
P	0.171	.743**	.681**	-.690**	.416*	1				
Cu	0.248	.640**	.714**	-.678**	.595**	.627**	1			
Zn	.511*	.697**	.745**	-.851**	.816**	.727**	.701**	1		
Fe	.547**	.442*	.532**	-.659**	.823**	.432*	0.397	.852**	1	
Mn	-.634**	.551**	.411*	-0.11	-0.255	0.305	0.366	0.15	-0.077	1

(*): Shows a significant correlation at the $p \leq 0.05$ level, (**): Shows a significant correlation at the $p \leq 0.01$ level

3.2. Effect of vermicompost applications on protein, starch, and yield in wheat

When examining the effects of VC applications on protein, starch, and yield in different wheat varieties, it was found that the variety factor was significant for starch content at $p \leq 0.05$ (4.96^{*}). This indicates that there is a statistically significant difference in starch levels among different wheat varieties. However, the effect of the variety factor on protein is not significant (0.17^{ns}), suggesting that the varieties do not create a noticeable difference in protein levels. On the other hand, the effect of rate is significant at the $p \leq 0.01$ level for protein (10.5^{**}), starch (11.6^{**}), and

yield (12.7^{**}), indicating that higher rates positively affect both protein and starch content, as well as yield. In conclusion, it can be stated that in VC applications, varieties are effective in terms of starch but do not create significant differences in protein content, while rate provides a noticeable improvement in both components and yield. Additionally, the interaction of variety*rate was not statistically significant, indicating that the combined effects of varieties and rate do not distinctly influence each other. Therefore, it can be concluded that the varieties do not show differences in determining the optimal rate for each variety (Table 5).

Table 5. Effect of vermicompost applications on protein, starch, and yield in wheat

Variety	Rate (kg da ⁻¹)	Protein (%)	Starch (%)	Yield (kg da ⁻¹)
Dinç	Control	10.9 ^{±1.19} c	55.7 ^{±0.90} a	469 ^{±11.4} bc
Dinç	100	11.3 ^{±0.44} c	54.4 ^{±0.95} ab	474 ^{±20.4} bc
Dinç	200	11.7 ^{±0.10} bc	52.5 ^{±1.29} ab	494 ^{±16.1} ab
Dinç	300	12.9 ^{±0.70} ab	51.4 ^{±3.10} b	536 ^{±10.5} a
Tekin	Control	11.0 ^{±0.56} c	54.1 ^{±1.53} ab	436 ^{±9.53} c
Tekin	100	11.3 ^{±0.61} c	53.8 ^{±0.50} ab	465 ^{±28.3} bc
Tekin	200	11.6 ^{±0.23} bc	52.3 ^{±2.02} ab	482 ^{±49.7} bc
Tekin	300	13.3 ^{±1.15} a	47.4 ^{±2.20} c	531 ^{±19.8} a
Variety		0.17 ^{ns}	4.96 [*]	2.33 ^{ns}
Rate		10.5 ^{**}	11.6 ^{**}	12.7 ^{**}
Variety*Rate		0.14 ^{ns}	1.42 ^{ns}	0.42 ^{ns}

(ns): not significant, (*): Statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$ level, (**): Statistically significant at $p \leq 0.01$ level

3.2.1. Protein

Protein content is one of the most crucial factors in determining the quality of bread wheat. The protein levels with different rates of VC application in bread wheat range from 10.9% to 13.3%. The lowest protein content was observed in the Dinç variety under the control (0 kg da⁻¹) treatments, while the highest protein content was found in the Tekin variety with 300 kg da⁻¹ VC application. In both wheat varieties, the highest protein contents were achieved with the 300 kg da⁻¹ VC application, showing an increase compared to the control (0 kg da⁻¹) groups (Table 5, Figure 1). Linking wheat quality and yield to a

single variable can be challenging as they are influenced by multiple factors including nutrition, irrigation, climate, management practices, soil characteristics and protein content. Specifically, in bread wheat, protein content is a critical factor for product quality. For wheat used in bread production, the protein content should be above 11% (Sade et al., 1999). According to Ünal (2002), the protein content in wheat varies between 6-22% depending on the wheat type, variety, production technique, and environmental conditions. In Turkey, the protein content of wheat ranges from 9-13% in durum wheat, 10-15% in bread wheat and 11-17% in durum wheat used for pasta production.

Figure 1. Effect of vermicompost applications on protein content in wheat

3.2.2. Starch

The starch content ranges from 47.4% to 55.7% across the treatments, with the lowest starch amount observed in the Tekin variety with 300 kg da⁻¹ VC applications and the highest amount found in the Dinç variety with no VC application (0 kg da⁻¹). Increased rates of VC resulted in a reduction in starch content in both wheat varieties compared to the control

(0 kg da⁻¹) groups (Table 5, Figure 2). Starch and protein, major chemical components in wheat, have a significant impact on bread quality (Bilgiçli and Soylu, 2016). The starch content is inversely proportional to the protein content (Maningat et al., 2009). As seen in Table 5, there is a decrease in starch content corresponding to the increase in protein content due to VC fertilization.

Figure 2. Effect of vermicompost applications on starch content in wheat

3.2.3. Yield

The yield of wheat ranges from 436 kg da⁻¹ to 536 kg da⁻¹ across the treatments. The lowest yield was observed in the Tekin variety with no VC application (0 kg da⁻¹), while the highest yield was obtained from the Dinç variety with 300 kg da⁻¹ VC applications. Increased rates of VC resulted in higher yield values compared to the control (0 kg da⁻¹) groups for both wheat varieties (Table 5, Figure 3). In a study using five different VC rates and chemical fertilizers (NPK) on *Brassica oleracea* var. *alba*, it was observed that increasing VC rates improved yield and quality characteristics in cabbage (Tavali et al., 2014). In *Phaseolus vulgaris* L., it was

reported that the application of VC (0-1 t ha⁻¹) had a positive effect on yield over three years compared to control groups, resulting in increased yield (Kalita et al., 2016). In a study on watermelon, the highest yield value of 5.48 kg was found with the application of 600 kg da⁻¹ VC (Ak-Göksu and Öztokat-Kuzucu, 2017). For tomato and cucumber under greenhouse conditions, different rates of VC improved seedling development, yield, and quality. The best results were obtained with 40% and 60% VC mixtures, as reported by Atmaca (2012). In *Zea mays* L. *indentata*, different levels of worm castings positively affected grain yield, with the highest yield observed at 750 kg da⁻¹ application (Özel, 2019).

Figure 3. Effect of vermicompost applications on yield in wheat

3.3. Effect of vermicompost applications on K and P in wheat

When examining the effects of VC applications on K and P content in different wheat varieties, it is observed that the variety factor has significant effects at $p \leq 0.01$ for K (455**) and at $p \leq 0.05$ for P (6.92*). This indicates that there are statistically significant differences in K and P levels among different wheat varieties. On the other hand, the rate factor also has significant effects on K (86.0**) and P (104**) at $p \leq 0.01$, suggesting that higher rates positively impact the nutrient content in

wheat. However, the interaction of variety and rate is not statistically significant for either K (1.99^{ns}) or P (0.97^{ns}), indicating that the combined effects of varieties and rates do not distinctly influence each other (Table 6). The potassium (K) and phosphorus (P) values obtained in the experiment exhibited higher standard errors in some treatments. This may be attributed to natural variation in plant material, soil heterogeneity, or differences in nutrient uptake mechanisms. However, statistical analyses revealed significant differences, and the data are considered reliable.

Table 6. Effect of vermicompost applications on K and P in wheat

Variety	Rate (kg da ⁻¹)	K (mg kg ⁻¹)		P
Dinç	Control	2258 ^f		808 ^f
Dinç	100	2325 ^e		862 ^{de}
Dinç	200	2326 ^e		889 ^{bc}
Dinç	300	2437 ^d		915 ^a
Tekin	Control	2448 ^{cd}		809 ^f
Tekin	100	2492 ^{bc}		847 ^e
Tekin	200	2512 ^b		874 ^{cd}
Tekin	300	2665 ^a		900 ^{ab}
Variety		455**		6.92*
Rate		86.0**		104**
Variety*Rate		1.99 ^{ns}		0.97 ^{ns}

(ns): not significant. (*): Statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$ level. (**): Statistically significant at $p \leq 0.01$ level

3.3.1 Potassium (K)

The effect of increasing rates of VC on K concentration in wheat grain samples ranged from 2258 mg kg⁻¹ to 2665 mg kg⁻¹. The lowest K concentration was observed in the Dinç variety with the control (0 kg da⁻¹) treatment, while the highest K concentration

was obtained from the Tekin variety with a 300 kg da⁻¹ VC application (Table 6, Figure 4). It was noted that with increasing amounts of VC applied to the soil, the presence of macro nutrients such as N, P, and K in the plant increased and the availability of these elements in the soil was found to be better (Werner, 1997). The decomposition of organic matter in

the soil increases the bioavailability of nutrients and enhances the soil's cation exchange capacity by providing more exchange sites for mineral nutrients. (Duxbury et al., 1989). The changes in potassium content

can be explained by the mineralization process of VC, which makes K more readily available to plants, and the application of VC, which enhances the soil's cation exchange capacity, making K more accessible to plant roots.

Figure 4. Effect of vermicompost applications on K in wheat

3.3.2. Phosphorus (P)

The effect of increasing rates of VC on P concentration ranged from 808 mg kg⁻¹ to 915 mg kg⁻¹. The lowest P amount was observed with the control (0 kg da⁻¹) treatments, while the highest P amount was obtained from the Dinç variety with a 300 kg da⁻¹ VC application (Table 6, Figure 5). Vermicompost application

has been reported to improve the physical structure of the soil in tomato-growing areas, increasing the amounts of K, P, Ca, and organic carbon (Azarmi et al., 2008). In a trial with sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.), different rates of VC (0, 200, 400 and 800 kg da⁻¹) significantly increased yield and P concentration according to plant analysis results (Büyükfiliz, 2016).

Figure 5. Effect of vermicompost applications on P in wheat

3.4. Effect of vermicompost applications on Cu, Zn, Fe and Mn in wheat

The effects of VC applications on the content of Cu, Zn, Fe, and Mn in different wheat varieties were examined, revealing that the variety factor was statistically insignificant for Cu (ns). However, significant effects were detected for Zn (10.9**), Fe (224**), and Mn

(75.1**) at the $p \leq 0.01$ level. These findings indicate that there are statistically significant differences in the levels of Zn, Fe, and Mn among different wheat varieties. Regarding the rate factor, it was found to have statistically significant effects on Cu, Zn, Fe, and Mn at the $p \leq 0.01$ level. Furthermore, concerning the variety*rate interaction, significant results were obtained for Cu (13.0**) and Fe (16.6**)

at the $p \leq 0.01$ level, and for Mn (4.13) at the $p \leq 0.05$ level; this indicates that the combined effects of varieties and rates can be distinctly effective in certain cases. However, the

interaction for Zn was found to be statistically insignificant (0.07^{ns}), suggesting that Zn's interaction with the variety and rate variables is not pronounced (Table 7).

Table 7. Effect of vermicompost applications on Cu, Zn, Fe and Mn in wheat

Variety	Rate (kg da ⁻¹)	Cu, Zn, Fe and Mn (mg kg ⁻¹)			
		Cu	Zn	Fe	Mn
Dinç	Control	3.95 ^d	24.3 ^f	25.7 ^e	38.4 ^b
Dinç	100	4.78 ^b	25.0 ^{ef}	23.0 ^f	37.6 ^{bc}
Dinç	200	3.97 ^d	27.2 ^d	26.5 ^{de}	36.7 ^{cd}
Dinç	300	4.90 ^b	31.2 ^b	28.2 ^b	39.8 ^a
Tekin	Control	4.05 ^{cd}	26.6 ^{df}	27.0 ^{cd}	35.9 ^{de}
Tekin	100	4.14 ^{cd}	27.3 ^d	27.4 ^c	35.1 ^e
Tekin	200	4.35 ^c	29.5 ^c	28.2 ^b	36.1 ^{de}
Tekin	300	5.47 ^a	33.5 ^a	30.8 ^a	37.3 ^{bc}
Variety		1.94 ^{ns}	10.9 ^{**}	224 ^{**}	75.1 ^{**}
Rate		50.7 ^{**}	22.3 ^{**}	121 ^{**}	19.9 ^{**}
Variety*Rate		13.0 ^{**}	0.07 ^{ns}	16.6 ^{**}	4.13 [*]

(ns): not significant. (*): Statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$ level. (**): Statistically significant at $p \leq 0.01$ level

3.4.1. Copper (Cu)

The concentration of Cu in wheat grains ranged from 3.95 mg kg⁻¹ to 5.47 mg kg⁻¹ with the lowest concentration in the Dinç variety under control (0 kg da⁻¹) applications and the highest concentration in the Tekin variety with 300 kg da⁻¹ VC applications (Table 7, Figure 6). A study on the effects of VC applications

on wheat nutrition showed increases in both macro (N, P, K, Mg and Ca) and micro (Fe, Zn, Mn and Cu) elements compared to control groups (Barlas et al., 2018). The significant increase in copper content can be associated with the Cu content of VC and the ability of organic matter to enhance the bioavailability of Cu for plant uptake.

Figure 6. Effect of vermicompost applications on Cu in wheat

3.4.2. Zinc (Zn)

The Zn concentration in wheat grains varied between 24.3 mg kg⁻¹ and 33.5 mg kg⁻¹. The lowest Zn concentration was observed in the Dinç variety under control (0 kg da⁻¹) applications, while the highest was found in the Tekin variety with 300 kg da⁻¹ VC applications (Table 7, Figure 7). A study on

tomato plants indicated that VC applications improved soil physical properties and increased Mn and Zn concentrations (Azarmi et al., 2008). Additionally, VC applications positively affected plant growth and soil properties for various plants, with increased Zn concentrations reported (Eryüksel, 2016). Zinc levels increased with higher VC application

rates, reaching a maximum at 300 kg da⁻¹. This suggests that the organic fertilizer may enhance uptake by providing Zn-binding ligands, as noted by Hamzah Saleem et al. (2022), who stated that the utilization of organic ligands results in the formation of

organic Zn compounds in soil, which can either increase or reduce Zn availability in soil and plant uptake. Smith (2009), the presence of organic matter causes dissolution of insoluble Zn, which increases the bioavailability of Zn.

Figure 7. Effect of vermicompost applications on Zn in wheat

3.4.3. Iron (Fe)

Iron (Fe) concentration in wheat grains ranged from 23.0 mg kg⁻¹ to 30.8 mg kg⁻¹. The lowest Fe concentration was found in the Dinç variety with 100 kg da⁻¹ VC applications, while the highest was observed in the Tekin variety with 300 kg da⁻¹ VC applications

(Table 7, Figure 8). Vermicompost applications generally increased Fe concentrations, although there was a decrease in Fe for the Dinç variety at 100 kg da⁻¹ VC compared to control groups. Increased Fe concentrations with VC applications were also reported for lettuce plants (Adiloğlu et al., 2015).

Figure 8. Effect of vermicompost applications on Fe in wheat

3.4.4. Manganese (Mn)

Manganese (Mn) concentration in wheat ranged from 35.1 mg kg⁻¹ to 39.8 mg kg⁻¹. The lowest Mn concentration was observed in the Tekin variety with 100 kg da⁻¹ VC applications, while the highest was found in the Dinç variety with 300 kg da⁻¹ VC applications (Table 7, Figure 9). Manganese concentrations varied with VC applications,

showing decreases at 100 and 200 kg da⁻¹ in the Dinç variety compared to control, but an increase at 300 kg da⁻¹. In the Tekin variety, Mn concentrations decreased at 100 kg da⁻¹ VC but increased at other rates. Vermicompost applications generally increased N, P, K, Mn, Zn, Fe, and S concentrations in lettuce, with the highest N, P and K levels at 200 kg da⁻¹ VC (Özen and Sönmez, 2019).

Figure 9. Effect of vermicompost applications on Mn in wheat

4. Conclusion

The study investigated the effects of VC applications on the yield and quality of bread wheat varieties. A yield increase of 12.5% for the Dinç variety and 17.9% for the Tekin variety was observed. Vermicompost applications resulted in the highest protein levels in both wheat varieties, with values of 12.9% and 13.3% at a rate of 300 kg da⁻¹. Additionally, increased VC rates led to a decrease in starch content. Vermicompost applications also resulted in increased K and P concentrations compared to control groups.

The research determined that different rates of VC applications affected the concentrations of some important micronutrients (Cu, Zn, Fe and Mn) in wheat grains. Generally, VC applications increased the concentrations of these elements, with the highest values achieved with 300 kg da⁻¹ VC applications. However, significant increases in micronutrient concentrations were observed with higher VC rates, with some exceptions. This suggests that VC enhances soil fertility, improves plant nutrient uptake and positively affects the nutrient content of grains. Differences in VC responses between the Dinç and Tekin varieties indicate that the effect of VC applications may vary depending on the plant variety. It can be concluded that VC can enhance micronutrient richness and improve product quality in wheat cultivation.

Overall, organic fertilizers, which consist of materials from plant, animal, and human sources, improve the physical, chemical, and biological properties of the soil, supporting yield increase. Unlike chemical fertilizers,

organic fertilizers maintain soil health and ecological balance in the long term. These fertilizers offer an environmentally friendly approach, promoting plant growth and playing a crucial role in restoring natural fertility.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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